

PIDMR

PID Meta Resolver

Partners working on this component

Component Overview

Persistent identifiers (PIDs) are used in all areas of scientific work. They are not only used for scholarly communication, but also support various data management processes. PIDMR is a generic resolver that makes it possible to resolve PIDs from a wide variety of systems and providers.

The service is active and offers various interfaces for interaction. PID resolution can take place both via a UI and integrated in data processing pipelines. It should be emphasised that, depending on the PID system or provider, either the metadata, the landing page or even the digital object can be delivered directly as the result of the query.

The last option in particular increases the machine processing of digital objects referenced with PID. There are currently around 50 different systems or providers registered. Each provider can register in the service and thus make their own PIDs resolvable via the PIDMR.

Functionalities

The PIDMR service receives a PID in the form of a string and evaluates the assignment to a system or provider. This information is clearly displayed in the UI. After the assignment, the possible methods of resolution, i.e. landing page, metadata or the digital object, are made available for selection.

The request is processed with the submit and the result is displayed to the user. When using APIs, the method can be transferred using a parameter. A detailed description of the API can be found in the documentation. Authentication via the EOSC AAI is available for the registration of new providers.

After successful verification, the provider information is maintained in a database and the PIDs of this provider can be resolved via PIDMR.

Impact

The PIDMR service standardises the resolution of PIDs. Due to the complexity of the current PID landscape, it is very difficult for individual scientists to integrate different PID systems into their workflows. Expert knowledge is no longer required to implement many different interfaces; a well-structured API with clear parameters is now available. The PIDMR service is a scalable and expandable solution that can be integrated into various use cases.

**Discover the
PIDMR Service**